

Exploring the Relationship between Sleep Habits, Fast Food Consumption and Physical Activity Levels in Young Adults: A Pakistan's Survey Study

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This study has no aim to hurt any ideological or social segment but is purely based on academic purposes.

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Abstract

This study investigates the relationship between physical activity, fast food consumption and sleep habits in young adults, with a specific focus on identifying predictors of sleep quality. A quantitative survey of 110 participants (ages 18-45) was conducted within Okara city (Pakistan), using a self-administered questionnaire to assess sleep habits, physical activity, and fast-food consumption. Multiple linear regression analysis revealed that physical activity and fast-food consumption were not significant predictors of sleep quality in this population. However, the findings suggest that other lifestyle factors, such as stress and screen time, may play a more significant role in shaping sleep habits in young adults. The results of this study have implications for the development of targeted interventions aimed at improving sleep quality and overall health outcomes in young adults.

Introduction

“The Trifecta of healthy lifestyle - balanced diet, regular exercise, and quality sleep is crucial for overall well-being”. (Matricciani et al., 2018)

There are numerous ways through which health is defined, but WHO (World Health Organization) has conceptualized health in a classical way in its contribution of 1948 as a comprehensive state of wellbeing that encompasses complete physical, social, and mental well-being and not merely the absence of diseases or infirmity (Vuori et al., 2013). Sleep, often under looked pillar of healthy lifestyle, play essential role in our overall wellbeing. (Matricciani et al., 2018) Sleep deprivation significantly contributed to mental health problems among students and many other serious health diseases in older adults (Milojevich & Lukowski, 2016; Blumenthal et al., 1988). Physical activity is a complex, multifaceted behavior. There are many different modes of physical activity that individuals perform throughout the day, such as occupational, household chores, including care giving and domestic cleaning, and active transportation like walking and cycling. Many leisure time activities are performed by people to maintain physical fitness. It includes dancing, swimming, etc. where the body undergoes repetitive movements to address health concerns (Miles, 2007).

Fast food is typically high in unhealthy nutrients, contributing to myriad of diseases. Its regular consumption exacerbates many diseases, such as weight gain, obesity, type 2 Diabetes, and coronary artery disease, and has a ripple effect on sleeping quality as well (Park et al., 2018; Min et al., 2018; Rasouli et al., 2021; Patel et al., 2008; Keyes et al., 2015; Carrier et al., 2017). This study is specifically designed to investigate the question: Do fast food consumption and physical activity levels predict sleep habits in young adults? This study is aimed to investigate influence of Physical Activity and Fast-food consumption on sleep habits among young adults aged 18 to 30, shedding light on the interconnectedness of these lifestyle factors

Literature Review

Sleep Habits and Health Outcomes

Studies have reportedly suggested that poor sleep habits are concerned with various health conditions.

A questionnaire-based study was conducted among the students of 69 universities characterized by healthy sleeping habits. The major objective of this research is to examine the association between sleep quality and mental health. Research was aimed at uncovering the relation between sleep quality and mental health of various students, particularly undergraduate students in universities. Findings revealed a growing rate of deteriorating sleep quality and mental health outcomes before they received serious consideration at the clinic (Milojevich & Lukowski, 2016). Research has consistently shown that sleep duration has been declining over the past 50 years. Many sleep problems, such as short sleep duration, disturbed sleep quality, and long sleep duration, are all associated with poor health outcomes. All this leads to an increased risk of metabolic disorders and cardiovascular diseases (Larcher et al., 2015). Additionally, a cross-sectional study was conducted to investigate the relationship between sleep timing, sleep consistency, and cardiovascular diseases, particularly in adults. However, this study found no significant correlation between sleep duration and heart disease (odds ratio (OR): 1.41, 95% confidence interval (CI): 0.96–2.06) (Slavish et al., 2019). One more study concluded that adults under the age of 60 who experience social jetlag are more likely to develop type 2 Diabetes (Koopman et al., 2017).

Various epidemiological studies revealed that there is strong association between sleep duration and health outcomes. For healthy lifestyle, studies suggested avoiding luxury sleep defined as more than 8 hours per day sleep or less than 7 hours per day sleep. Individuals who sleep outside optimal range are at higher risk of mortality, cardiovascular disease, and diabetes. However, it is worth noting that there are limitations in the study as the data is not definitive and further research is needed (Alvarez & Ayas, 2004). Meta-analysis of 137 prospective cohort studies revealed that long sleep duration is significantly associated with high health risks including mortality, diabetes mellitus, cardiovascular disease, stroke, coronary heart disease and obesity. Conversely, long sleep is insignificantly associated with hypertension. However, data is insufficient to conclude findings for depression and dyslipidemia (Jike et al., 2017).

The Wisconsin Health Survey (2008–2012) conducted a cross-sectional study in which 1593 individuals participated and examined particular characteristics in work (traditional, shift work), sleep habits, and sleep problems (insomnia, insufficient sleep, and wake-time sleepiness). This study revealed that shift workers face disturbances in metabolic health due to insufficient sleep patterns. Although more definite studies are needed by health care providers to identify individuals with high risk and address resulting health disparities (Bowman & Vinyard, 2004). Another study was conducted on shift workers by the International Agency for Research on Cancer in 2007, which revealed circadian disruption in shift workers is classified as a probable human carcinogen, highlighting a potential cancer risk in shift workers (Blumenthal et al., 1988). Another study revealed a relationship between sleep variability and type 2 Diabetes. In elderly people with high cardiovascular risk, sleep duration and sleep variability are both closely linked with obesity and type 2 diabetes (Blumenthal et al., 1988b).

Fast Food Consumption and Health Outcomes

Analysis showed that there is a difference in diet between individuals with short sleep duration and those with normal sleep duration. It is marked that people with a short sleep pattern consume a narrow range of food choices with a lesser intake of macronutrients like protein, carbohydrates, fiber, and fats (Khan et al., 2020). A comparative study revealed that fast food consumers intake a high amount of energy, fat, saturated fatty acids (SFAs), trans fatty acids (TFAs), added sugar and sodium, and lower intakes of fiber, macronutrients, and vitamins as compared to those who prepare their meals at home. This research indicates that fast food consumers tend to have diets high in poor nutrients (Park et al., 2018; Min et al., 2018; Rasouli et al., 2021; Patel et al., 2008).

Contrary to previous findings, an observational study revealed that high intake of fats is strongly correlated with various sleeping disorders. Suggesting that high fat intake negatively affects sleep quality (Keyes et al., 2015). A comprehensive research analysis indicated that fast food consumption is highly associated with weight gain, obesity, type 2 Diabetes, and coronary artery disease, underscoring the unhealthy nature of fast food (Carrier et al., 2017).

Physical Activity Levels and Health Outcomes

Furthermore, regular physical activity has a profound impact on psychological wellness by significantly lowering levels of stress, anxiety, and depression (Chaput et al., 2016; Shochat et al., 2014; Grummon et al., 2020). Research has explored the relationship between physical activity and morality across diverse occupations such as postal workers, railroad workers, and farm workers, employees of utility companies, civil servants, longshoremen, policemen, and firefighters. A questionnaire-based study revealed that there is a strong link between a reduction in risk of coronary heart disease and an increase in physical

activity, highlighting the importance of exercise in mitigating cardiovascular disease (O'Connor et al., 1998; Atkinson & Davenne, 2007).

Low-intensity exercise is defined as exercise of at least 45% of maximum aerobic power, associated with enhancement in health outcomes, particularly in cardiovascular disease (Dibben et al., 2023). The Health Study of Nurses is landmark research that concluded that physical activity is highly associated with lowered mortality risk in women of all characterized body weights (Erren & Reiter, 2009; Gong et al., 2017). A substantial body of evidence indicates that routine physical activity reduces cancer risk by approximately 46% (Ofstedal et al., 2019). An investigation into the effect of aerobic exercise of moderate intensity on stage 2 hypertension and left ventricular hypertrophy in veterans male. A significant reduction was observed in blood pressure and left ventricular mass regression after 16 weeks of regular exercise. Moreover, after 32 weeks of regular exercise, blood pressure significantly lowered even after a 33% reduction in antihypertensive medication. It is concluded through a study that exercise is related to a reduction in blood pressure, whereas no changes have been seen in the blood pressure of the group with zero exercise, suggesting that exercise is a valuable adjunct to pharmacological therapy in managing hypertension (Moreira et al., 2010).

Interplay between Sleep Habits, Fast Food Consumption, and Physical Activity Levels

Poor lifestyle is a significant contributor to mental distress in both genders, male and female. A study reported that frequent increases in mental distress are highly linked with bad lifestyles and suboptimal dietary practices (Warburton et al., 2001). In order to control blood pressure, many factors encompass a healthy lifestyle approach, such as less intake of salt and fats in diet, weight loss, and improved physical activities (World Health Organization, 2002; Grimm et al., 1997). Global School-based student Health Survey data analyzed fast food consumption in adolescent males and females. A comparative study revealed that males who consumed fast food for more than 4 days per week had a 55% greater risk of sleep disturbance compared to those who consumed fast food less than 1 day per week. Similarly, females had 50% higher odds of sleep disturbance (Foti et al., 2011).

A recent study conducted in South Korea examined the sleep patterns of adolescents. The study revealed that individuals with high consumption of fast food such as pizza, hamburgers, and fried chicken, as well as carbonated drinks including soda, had reduced odds of satisfactory sleep (Kredlow et al., 2015). Sleep disturbances such as short sleep duration and poor quality sleep are characterized by increased consumption of unhealthy food items, including sugar-sweetened beverages, fast food, instant noodles, and confectionaries. Moreover, inadequate consumption of nutritious food items like fruits, vegetables, and milk is another significant factor that disturbs sleep (Wang & Boros, 2019). Research demonstrated a cluster of lifestyle factors that are interrelated, such as a low number of family members, daily fast food consumption, stress status, poor sleep quality, and odds of eating disorders. Further longitudinal studies are necessary to confirm these findings (Atoui et al., 2020).

Research has identified that in adolescents there is a correlation between inadequate sleep and an increased risk of metabolic consequences of weight gain and obesity (Patel et al., 2008). Reports highlighted the growing prevalence of short sleep duration in children and adolescents, which is highly linked with elevated BMI as well as the other adverse health effects (Kruger et al., 2014). It is evident in researches that there is a close association between sleep, physical activity, and increasing obesity. Additionally, it is more clearly stated that long sleep duration and short sleep duration both are significant causes of increasing obesity. Adequate sleep duration is therefore necessary for a healthy lifestyle (Horne

& Moore, 1985). Research demonstrated that acute exercise has a minimum level of impact on sleep duration. However, a detailed study showed that regular exercise has little significant effect on sleep time and efficiency, while sleep onset latency is affected from a small to medium level, which has beneficial outcomes. Furthermore, sleep quality is also influenced to a moderate degree (Kredlow et al., 2015).

The National Youth Risk Behavior Survey (2009) among 9th and 10th grade students to examine the correlation between physical activity and sleep conducted a study. Findings revealed that regular physical activity of about 60 minutes or greater is directly associated with sufficient sleep among adolescents who had limited computer use (Foti et al., 2011). A growing body of evidence suggested that moderate levels of physical exercise yield more beneficial health effects as compared to vigorous exercise. However, more research is required to be done under consideration of various social factors, such as age, for better health outcomes and to inform evidence-based recommendations (Wang & Boros, 2019). An observational study was conducted to examine the relationship between sleep and physical activity in women with breast cancer. The study concluded that there is no statistically significant difference in sleep pattern between participants with high levels of physical activity and those who engage in low levels of physical activity (Atoui et al., 2020).

Factors Influencing Sleep Habits, Fast Food Consumption, and Physical Activity Levels

Sleep patterns are influenced by various demographic factors of the population, including age distribution, economic development, work hours, technology use, and culture. As a result, sleep patterns vary significantly across different countries and populations. The older population tends to take less sleep (Patel et al., 2008). Studies have found that sleep pattern differ between individuals in different gender, with girls tend to sleep less than 7 hours sleep whereas boys tend to sleep more (Keyes et al., 2015). The effects of ageing on sleep quality appear to be sex-dependent, with women showing a greater increase in sleep disturbances with age, whereas men experience less severe changes (Carrier et al., 2017). Sleep quality is closely tied to an individual's emotional state and behavioral changes. Emotional challenges like anxiety and depression are associated with sleep quality. Moreover, intense behaviors such as aggression and bullying are all linked with sleep disturbance (Chaput et al., 2016; Shochat et al., 2014).

Bedtime habits could be an innovative strategy to improve sleep duration and diet intake. It is observed that later bedtime is related to short sleep duration and leads to unhealthy eating behaviors (Grummon et al., 2020). Many factors are associated with sleep quality problems that have adverse effects on health, such as duration of sleep and sleep timing. Moreover, studies claimed that the habit of going to bed early (early chronotype) versus the ability of going to bed later (late chronotype) are notably associated with social schedules such as school and work routine (Larcher et al., 2015). The sleep-wake cycle is a prominent circadian rhythm in humans. Sleep initiates when body temperature drops, and individuals wake up when body temperature rises. However, to validate these findings, additional physiological measurements are required (O'Connor et al., 1998). For optimizing good sleep quality, it is important to understand the transition phase between physical activities and sleep initiation. Additionally, investigating thermoregulatory mechanisms and pineal functions can elucidate the intricate relationship between physical activities and sleep pattern (Atkinson & Davenne, 2007).

The effects of exercise on sleep outcomes were moderated by several factors, including participant sex, age, baseline physical activity level, and exercise type, time of day, duration, and adherence. However, no significant moderation was observed for exercise intensity, aerobic/anaerobic classification, or

publication date (Kredlow et al., 2015). In today's digital age, students are more indulged in use of electronic devices such as computers, iPhones, and iPads, which is a major contributor to sleep deprivation among adolescents (Dibben et al., 2023). A study identifies that exposure to light in biological night disrupts the circadian system and alters sleep activity. Moreover, it suppresses melatonin production and deregulates circadian genes related to metabolic pathways (Erren & Reiter, 2009). A study revealed that Chinese adolescents are particularly susceptible to sleep deprivation due to intense academic pressure (Gong et al., 2017). Research examined three key aspects of a healthy lifestyle (physical activity, diet quality, sitting, and sleep). It is concluded that all these patterns are associated with sociodemographic variables including smoking, weight status, and mental distress (alcohol consumption was not considered). Out of all three lifestyle patterns, the study emphasized that poor sleep behavior is significantly related to mental distress (Oftedal et al., 2019).

The association between physical activity and coronary heart disease has been found independent of demographic factors such as gender, age (same for both men and women), and other risk factors such as smoking, hypercholesterolemia, and hypertension (O'Connor et al., 1998; Atkinson & Davenne, 2007). Two comprehensive reports of the study analyzed the correlation of physical activity with reduced mortality risk, controlling potential for various factors of age, smoking status, parental history of coronary heart disease, menopause, hormonal use, and alcohol consumption (Erren & Reiter, 2009; Gong et al., 2017). The present study identified eight distinct dietary patterns (vegetables, pulses, fruit, olive oil; fish, meat, processed meats, eggs, and starchy foods; vegetable soup, olive oil, butter, starchy foods, and bread; fast food, SSB, and pastry; olive oil, butter, and margarine; yoghurt, cheese, and ice cream; crackers/cookies, and pastry; milk, milk pudding, and ready-to-eat cereals). The study revealed that longer sleeping durations were positively associated with dietary patterns that included vegetables, pulses, fruit, olive oil, and vegetable soup and negatively associated with fast food, SSS, and pastry intake (Moreira et al., 2010).

Gaps in Current Research

Previous studies have primarily focused on the individual effect of physical activity and fast food consumption on sleep habits and overall health, leaving a significant research gap in the literature regarding the simultaneous effect of physical activity and fast food consumption on sleep habits in young adults. The interplay between these factors and collective influence on this population remains poorly understood. This notable gap in the literature highlights the need for a comprehensive examination of the synergistic effect of physical activity and fast food consumption on sleep habits in young adults.

Methodology

This quantitative study investigated the relationship between physical activity, fast food consumption, and sleep habits in young adults.

Participants

A convenience sample of 110 young adults (ages 18-45) participated in this study, from the Okara city of Pakistan.

Data Collection

A self-administrated survey assessed;

- Sleep habits: bedtime, sleep duration, sleep quality, and frequency of fast-food consumption.
- Physical activity: frequency, type and duration.
- Demographics: age and gender.

Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics and frequency distributions summarized participant characteristics. Correlation analysis (Pearson's r) examined relationships between physical activity, fast food consumption, and sleep habits. Linear regression analysis predicted sleep habits based on physical activity and fast-food consumption.

Results

Descriptive Analysis

Sleep Habits

Variables	Mean	Median	Mode	Std. Dev.
Bedtime	2.14	2	2	0.70
Sleep Duration	1.76	2	2	1.23
Sleep Quality	2.65	3	3	0.76
Fast Food Consumption	3.17	3	3	0.74

Table 1. Descriptive statistics (mean, median, mode, standard deviation) for sleep habits and fast-food consumption variables, based on self-reported data from 110 young adults. Scale: Bedtime (1 = Before 10pm, 2 = 10pm-12am, 3 = After 12am), Sleep Duration (hours), Sleep Quality (1 = Poor (1-2), 2 = Fair(3-4), 3 = Good(5-6), 4 = Excellent(7-8), Fast Food Consumption (1 = Daily, 2 = 3-4 times/week, 3 = 1-2 times/week, 4 = Rarely).

Physical Activity

Variables	Mean	Median	Mode	Std. Dev.
Frequency	2.39	3	1	1.27
Type	3.36	4	1	1,81
Duration	1.84	1.84	2	1

Table 2. Descriptive statistics (mean, median, mode, standard deviation) for physical activity variables, based on self-reported data from 110 young adults. Scales: Physical Activity Frequency (1 = Daily, 2 = 3-4 times/week, 3 = 1-2 times/week, 4 = Rarely), Physical Activity Type (1 = No activity, 2 = Household chores,

3 = Run, 4 = Walk, 5 = Exercise, 6 = Sports), Physical Activity Duration (1 = Less than 30 minutes, 2 = 30-60 minutes, 3 = 1-2 hours, 4 = More than 2 hours).

Demographics

Age

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
18-24	66	60%
25-34	29	26.36%
35-44	11	10%
45 or older	4	3.63

Table 3. Age distribution of the study sample (N = 110), Self-reported data from young adults.

Gender

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Female	65	59.09%
Male	45	40.91%

Table 4. Gender distribution of the study sample (N = 110), Self-reported data from young adults.

Correlation Analysis

	Physical Activity	Fast Food
Sleep Quality	-0.1777	-0.160
Sleep Duration	-0.0470	0.120
Bedtime	0.1413	0.1059

Table 5. Correlation analysis results examining relationships between physical activity, fast food consumption, and sleep habits variables. Pearson's r values indicate strength and direction of relationships.

Regression Analysis

Predictor	Slope	t-statistic	p-value
Physical Activity	-0.1064	0.07299	0.9419
Fast Food Consumption	-0.6017		

Intercept	2.7935
R ²	-0.01933
Standard Error	-0,7935
Standard Deviation	0.0725

Table 6. Linear regression analysis examined the relationship between lifestyle factors (physical activity, fast food consumption) and sleep quality. Results indicate no significant predictors ($p > 0.05$).

Discussion

- The study aimed to explore the relationship between physical activity, fast food consumption, and sleep habits in young adults. The findings suggest that physical activity and fast-food consumption do not significantly predict sleep habits in this population.
- The correlation analysis revealed weak relationships between physical activity and sleep quality ($r = -0.1777$), sleep duration ($r = -0.0470$), and bedtime ($r = 0.1413$). Similarly, fast food consumption showed no significant association with sleep quality ($r = -0.060$), sleep duration ($r = 0.120$), or bedtime ($r = 0.1059$).
- The regression analysis supported these findings, indicating no significant predictive relationship between physical activity ($p = 0.9419$) or fast-food consumption and sleep habits.
- These results contradict previous studies suggesting a strong link between physical activity and sleep quality. However, they align with research indicating that fast food consumption has minimal impact on sleep habits.

Limitations

Young adults' sleep habits may be influenced by factors beyond physical activity and fast-food consumption, such as stress, social media use, or academic/work demands. The study's sample size and demographic characteristics may have limited the detection of significant relationships.

Conclusion

This study contributes to the understanding of lifestyle factors influencing sleep habits in young adults. The findings suggest that physical activity and fast-food consumption may not be significant predictors of sleep habits in this population.

Future Directions

Investigate other lifestyle factors influencing sleep habits (e.g., stress, social media use). Conduct longitudinal studies to examine causal relationships. Explore interventions targeting sleep improvement in young adults.

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